

Newsletter n°3 – March 2024

HORIZON EUROPE Programme GA No. 101057404

Welcome to the third ZDZW project newsletter!

After eighteen months of the **ZDZW** project, significant milestones have been achieved. We've embarked on our **beta testing campaign**, marking a pivotal step forward. Additionally, the **first ZDZW webinar** has successfully taken place, and we're thrilled to announce the prepared **schedule for upcoming ZDZW webinars**.

Throughout this journey, we continue to actively participate in major **international fairs and conferences**, contribute to **scientific publications**, held **plenary meetings**, and numerous consortium meetings. These interactions have been crucial in fostering synergies to achieve our ambitious project goals.

Join our expanding community and stay updated with our newsletter to learn how the **ZDZW** project can transform your manufacturing processes!

More info is available on the website (www.zdzw-project.eu).

ZDZW Webinar Series

Are you interested in the **latest NDI techniques, sustainable manufacturing and machine learning trends?**

If so, the **ZDZW** project offers you, **from Feb 2024 to April 2025**, the opportunity to expand your knowledge in various cutting-edge topics:

Know more about ZDZW webinars!

1 Unveiling the Latest NDI

2 Harnessing Machine Learning for Manufacturing Excellence

3 Strategies for Sustainable Manufacturing Practices

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Get to know the ZDZW's Webinar Schedule!

The coming months will be full of interesting learnings, as a series of webinars are scheduled to be delivered by ZDZW's various partners.

Read on to find out all the details!

[Explore our website for further details on upcoming/past webinars!](#)

OPEN FOR REGISTRATION!

Upcoming ZDZW Webinars...

DIGITAL TWIN APPLICATIONS FOR INDUSTRIAL THERMOFORMING

- 15:00 CET
- Organised by **SIMULARGE**
- [Registration link](#)

Key topics:

- Short Introduction to Thermoforming
- Digital Twin Applications in the Industry
- Modeling of Heating Stages in Thermoforming
- Data Acquisition and Calibration
- An Industrial Use Case

STATE-OF-THE-ART FOR NDI TECHNOLOGIES FROM SUSTAINABILITY PERSPECTIVE (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **EurA** **zabala**
INNOVATION

WELD INSPECTION WITH EMAT (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **Innerspec**
High-performance NDT solutions

AI APPLIED TO AV FOR QUALITY INSPECTION IN INDUSTRIAL DOMAIN: TECHNOLOGIES, EXAMPLES AND INSIGHTS (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **VIDEOSYSTEMS**

OCT AS A NON-DESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION TECHNOLOGY (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **NORBLIS** **DTU**
NORDIC BROADBAND LIGHT SOLUTIONS

www.zdzw-project.eu

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... and more upcoming **ZDZW Webinars!**

STATE-OF-THE-ART OF ML-BASED 3D OBJECT DETECTION AND CLASSIFICATION FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **Fraunhofer**
IGD

AI-BASED THERMAL IMAGING INSPECTION FOR THERMOFORMING (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **SIEMENS**

WEBINAR ON DATA ANNOTATION, MANUAL AND AUTOMATIC, WITH LAB TRAINING (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE VALÈNCIA**

WELD INSPECTION USING PROCESS MONITORING DATA (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **aimen**
TECHNOLOGY CENTRE

VISUAL NDI FROM MULTIPLE IMAGES (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **ITI** INVESTIGATE TO INNOVATE

HYBRID DIGITAL TWINS AS NDI TECHNIQUES FOR MANUFACTURING PROCESSES (REGISTRATION PENDING)

Organised by **ikerlan**

Past Webinars:

Acoustic Emission for Bearing Failure Detection

Last February 29th took place the 1st **ZDZW** webinar, in which we deepened in **Acoustic Emission as an NDI technique for failure detection applications** in the framework of Predictive Maintenance.

The **main topics** covered were:

- ➔ Acoustic Emission Technique
- ➔ Predictive Maintenance Framework
- ➔ Slow-rotating Bearing Failure

Organised by **Dira**

[Watch the 1st ZDZW webinar](#)

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What is happening in the ZDZW project?

4 Conference publications

7 Events [fairs, conferences, workshops]

Scientific publications

CONFERENCE PUBLICATIONS

Photonics West SPIE-OPTO Conference 2024
Looking into eggs by mid-infrared OCT for non-destructive inspection [Oral presentation - Article]
February 2024

Photonics West SPIE-LASE Conference 2024
Mid-IR supercontinuum noise reduction by SPM [Oral presentation]
February 2024

Photonics West SPIE-LASE Conference 2024
Noise characterization of mid-infrared supercontinuum generated through gain-switched pumping. [Article]
February 2024

Photonics West SPIE-OPTO Conference 2024
Non-destructive inspection of wind turbine blades with mid-infrared optical coherence tomography [Oral presentation]
February 2024

Events

Web Summit Qatar Coming February 23-26, 2025

Web Summit Qatar Coming February
23-29/2/2024

MATTCH 2.0 webinar organized by FBA to present ZDZW solutions
20/02/2024

ZDZW Webinar with Dira Reliability
29/02/2024

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What is happening in the ZDZW project?

Participation in SAMUEXPO 2024
01-03/02/2024

SPIE. PHOTONICS WEST
Photonics West
The world's premier event for lasers, biomedic optics and biophotonic technologies, quantum, optoelectronics
Sign up for emails

Participation in the SPIE Photonics west exhibition
30/01/2024 - 01/02/2024

5th Plenary meeting in Madrid
29/01/2023 - 02/02/2024

Advisory group meeting
02/02/2024

Participate in the ZDZW Open Beta Testing Pilot!

Be a pioneer in **manufacturing innovation** by testing 1 of our 11 inspection solutions.

Become an **early adopter of groundbreaking technologies** that will elevate your manufacturing process to new heights.

Apply now and secure your spot at the forefront of industry advancements!

Watch the ZDZW Open Beta Testing Pilot video

Join the ZDZW community to keep you up to date with the ZDZW project evolution!

ZERO DEFECT WASTE

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